

To Compare The Effect Of Topical 0.5% Loteprednol Etabonate Versus 0.09% Bromfenac On Macular Thickness Following Nd:Yag Laser Capsulotomy In A Tertiary Care Hospital

Sukhmanjit Kaur¹, Suman Bhartiya², Prachi Shukla³, Yashika Sinha⁴, Narendra Singh⁵

¹Junior Resident Department of Ophthalmology, Muzaffarnagar Medical College

²Professor And Head Department of Ophthalmology, Muzaffarnagar Medical College

³Professor Department of Ophthalmology, Muzaffarnagar Medical College

⁴Assistant Professor Department of Ophthalmology Muzaffarnagar Medical College

⁵Assistant Professor Department of Ophthalmology Muzaffarnagar Medical College

Received: 18-08-2024 / Revised: 16-09-2024 / Accepted: 28-10-2024

Corresponding Author: Prachi Shukla

Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract

Objective: To compare the effect of topical 0.5% Loteprednol etabonate versus 0.09% Bromfenac on Macular thickness after Nd:YAG laser capsulotomy and to compare the efficacy of Loteprednol and Bromfenac in preventing Cystoid macular edema.

Methodology: It is a hospital based prospective randomised comparative study in which patients who developed PCO after uncomplicated cataract surgery were included in the study. Patients were randomly distributed in two groups 175 each, out of total 350 patients. Patients were prescribed topical 0.5% Loteprednol etabonate in Group 1 and topical 0.09% Bromfenac in Group two after undergoing Nd: YAG laser capsulotomy. Visual acuity with snellen's chart, IOP with non-contact tonometer, and macular thickness with OCT was assessed at 1 hour, 1 week, and 4 weeks after the procedure in both the groups.

Results: The study recorded a significant improvement in visual acuity in both groups over time, with a notable percentage of patients achieving near-normal vision post-treatment. Also, there was no statistically significant difference observed in IOP and CMT among both the groups after the procedure.

Conclusion: The research concluded equal efficacy of Loteprednol Etabonate and bromfenac on central macular thickness and other parameters post Nd YAG capsulotomy procedure.

Keywords: Posterior capsule opacification, Nd:YAG laser capsulotomy, intraocular pressure, Cystoid macular edema

This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.

Introduction

The primary cause of treatable blindness in India is cataract, accounting for around 62.6% of all cases of blindness [1]. Probably the most common eye surgery performed globally is cataract surgery. Posterior capsule opacification (PCO) is the main problem that comes up after cataract surgery [2]. PCO presents with a notable decrease in visual sharpness and contrast [3].

In the two years following cataract surgery, posterior capsular opacification (PCO), which can range from 7% to 31%, is a usual post-operative complication. Visual acuity is significantly affected by posterior capsular opacification (PCO), which is located in the center 3 mm of the posterior capsule [3].

Neodymium: yttrium aluminium garnet (Nd:YAG) laser capsulotomy is a secure, non-invasive, and well-established method for treating PCO [4]. The enhancement of visual acuity, improvement in

glare minimization and contrast perception following Nd: YAG laser capsulotomy in individuals with notable posterior capsule opacification has been extensively recorded [5]. However, it can lead to serious consequences like retinal detachment, increased intraocular pressure (IOP), intraocular lens pitting, cystoid macular edema(CME) and corneal damage [6-8]. An Nd:YAG laser capsulotomy can lead to immediate postoperative inflammation, which reduces over the following days and persists as subclinical inflammation. According to literature, topically applied steroids along with nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory medicines can help reduce inflammation-related issues like CME after a Nd:YAG laser capsulotomy, since inflammation in the eye is only expected to be short term and mild [9].

Currently, there is no agreement on a superior or preferred option between steroids and nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory medicines. It is well known that NSAIDs have better side effect profile as compared to steroids, so it would be beneficial to use topical NSAID instead of topical steroid in patients of post Nd:YAG capsulotomy. However very few studies are available comparing the efficacy of topical steroids and NSAID in reducing CME post Nd:YAG capsulotomy. So, this study has been done to further enhance our knowledge regarding the comparative efficacy of bromfenac and loteprednol on central macular thickness.

Materials and Method

This is a hospital based prospective randomised comparative study conducted after clearance from Board of Studies and Ethical Committee in the Department of Ophthalmology, Muzaffarnagar medical college, Muzaffarnagar. All patients diagnosed with PCO on slit lamp examination between the age group of 40 to 80 years, both male and female with BCVA < 6/9 following uncomplicated cataract surgery with posterior chamber lens implantation with no active ocular inflammation or infection, who were willing to participate after informed consent were taken in the study. Patients with refractive error greater than -2/+2 dioptres, H/O ocular surgery other than cataract surgery within 3 months, patients who have known hypersensitivity to the study drugs, H/O ocular trauma and patients having systemic disorders like diabetes mellitus and hypertension and/or ocular disorder like age related macular degeneration were excluded from the study. Duration period of study was 18 months.

The sample size of 350 was taken based on the number of After cataract/PCO patients who attended Ophthalmology OPD, MMC&H, in the last 5 years.

All patients were treated with Nd:YAG laser posterior capsulotomy. Nd:YAG laser energy was set between 2-6mJ and laser was focused on the posterior capsule and capsulotomy was performed. A 3mm capsulotomy size was kept.

Patients were randomly divided into two groups. In Group one, patients were given topical 0.5% Loteprednol etabonate QID for 1st week, TDS for

2nd week, BD for 3rd week and OD for 4th week: Day 0 to Day 28. In Group two, patients received topical 0.09% Bromfenac BD for 4 weeks: Day 0 to Day 28.

All patients were examined before the procedure, 1 h after the procedure, at 1 week and at 4 weeks. All patients underwent a complete ocular examination including best corrected visual acuity (BCVA) on a Snellen scale, Slit-lamp bio-microscopy, Non-contact tonometry, and Indirect ophthalmoscopy. Biomicroscopic retro illumination technique was used to examine PCO and OCT (Heidelberg Spectralis SD-OCT) was done to evaluate central macular thickness.

Results

The study included 350 patients, divided equally into Groups 1 and 2, each with 175 participants. In Group 1, 56% of the patients were male and 44% were female. In Group 2, 53.1% of the patients were male and 46.9% were female.

The study analysed changes in central macular thickness (CMT) before treatment, 1 hour after treatment, 1 week after treatment, and 1 month after treatment among 350 patients divided equally into Group 1 and Group 2. In Group 1, the CMT was 258.7±15.5 microns before treatment, 259.2±14.5 microns, 1 hour after treatment, 260.7±15.7 microns, 1 week after treatment, and 263.6±16.6 microns, 1 month after treatment. In Group 2, the CMT was 260.0±26.6 microns before treatment, 262.0±23.6 microns, 1 hour after treatment, 263.7±22.9 microns, 1 week after treatment, and 266.4±28.5 microns, 1 month after treatment as shown in Graph 1. The p-value of 0.40 indicated a statistically insignificant difference in the changes in central macular thickness over time between the two groups.

A statistically significant difference in the changes in best-corrected visual acuity over time in both the two groups with p-value of 0.001 was noted. In both groups, BCVA improved significantly as shown in Graph 2. The p-value of 1.69 indicated a statistically insignificant difference in the changes in intraocular pressure over time between the two groups. None of the groups had raised IOP after Nd YAG capsulotomy as shown in Graph 3.

Discussion

Posterior capsule opacification (PCO) is a late complication of cataract surgery resulting from cytokine stimulation of residual lens epithelial cells, surgical damage, and type of intraocular lens used.[10,11] Nd YAG laser posterior capsulotomy is a non-invasive and reliable treatment for PCO, which may lead to complications like IOL damage, glaucoma, retinal detachment, CME.[12] Following Nd YAG laser capsulotomy, the incidence of CME ranges from 0.7 to 3%. This is because the presence of inflammatory mediators such as prostaglandins increases peri-foveal capillary permeability. [13]

Following cataract surgery and laser capsulotomy, steroid and nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory eye drops are commonly prescribed to treat pain and inflammation.[14] Topical steroids are very effective for managing inflammation but may lead to rise of intraocular pressure. On the contrary, topical nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory medications (NSAIDs), while being efficient in reducing pain and inflammation, have no effect on intraocular pressure (IOP).[15]

In our study after Nd YAG capsulotomy, Group 1 was administered topical 0.5% Loteprednol etabonate at a frequency of four times daily for the first week, three times daily for the second week, twice daily for the third week, and once daily for the fourth week. Group 2 was administered a topical solution of 0.09% Bromfenac twice daily for a duration of four weeks, starting from Day 0 and ending on Day 28. Our study looked at changes in central macular thickness (CMT) at several times: before therapy, one hour after treatment, one week after treatment, and one month after treatment. The central macular thickness (CMT) in Group 1 was measured to be 258.7±15.5 microns before treatment, 259.2±14.5 microns, 1 hour after treatment, 260.7±15.7 microns, 1 week after treatment, and 263.6±16.6 microns, 1 month after treatment. The central macular thickness (CMT) in Group 2 was measured to be 260.0±26.6 microns before treatment, 262.0±23.6 microns, 1 hour after treatment, 263.7±22.9 microns, 1 week after treatment, and 266.4±28.5 microns, 1 month after treatment. The p-value of 0.40 suggests a statistically insignificant disparity in the alterations of central macular thickness over time between the two groups. Elmazlom et al. also discovered that one week following Nd:YAG capsulotomy, there was a negligible increase in CMT.[16] A negligible increase in macular thickness was noted by Parajuli et al. one week and four weeks following the treatment.[17]

The baseline best-corrected visual acuity (BCVA) in Group 1 was 0.40 ± 0.15. One hour after treatment, the BCVA increased to 0.49 ± 0.28. After one week, the BCVA further improved to

0.89 ± 0.18, and after one month, it reached 0.90 ± 0.21. Within Group 2, the best-corrected visual acuity (BCVA) was measured to be 0.33 ± 0.16 prior to therapy, 0.39 ± 0.19, one hour after treatment, 0.77 ± 0.28, one week after treatment, and 0.82 ± 0.08, one month after treatment. The p-value of 0.001 demonstrated a statistically significant disparity in the alterations in best-corrected visual acuity over time in both groups i.e., BCVA significantly improved in both the groups. Moon *et. al.* compared the effects of topical 0.5% loteprednol etabonate and 0.09% Bromfenac on macular thickness. The study found no connection between BCVA and the impact of various treatments [18].

In Group 1, the IOP was 14.50±6.73 mmHg before treatment, reached 17.79±5.98 mmHg, 1 hour after treatment, then 15.44±4.90 mmHg, 1 week after treatment, and 13.21±3.69 mmHg, 1 month after treatment. In Group 2, the IOP was 14.40±5.46 mmHg before treatment, reached 17.01±5.11 mmHg, 1 hour after treatment, then 15.36±4.87 mmHg, 1 week after treatment, and 13.03±2.79 mmHg, 1 month after treatment. A statistically insignificant difference in the intraocular pressure changes over time between the two groups was revealed by the p-value of 1.69. According to a study by Amon et al., loteprednol etabonate barely affects intraocular pressure (IOP). Loteprednol etabonate is a secure option for treating inflammation after Nd YAG capsulotomy [19].

Conclusion

This study conducted at Muzaffarnagar Medical College effectively compared the outcomes of topical 0.5% Loteprednol Etabonate versus 0.09% Bromfenac on macular thickness after Nd:YAG laser capsulotomy. The research conclusively showed that both treatments are effective. Moreover, the study recorded a significant improvement in visual acuity in both groups over time, with a notable percentage of patients achieving near-normal vision levels post-treatment.

The data regarding the central macular thickness showed that after Nd YAG laser capsulotomy, treatment with Loteprednol Etabonate and Bromfenac in group 1 and 2 respectively showed favourable outcomes in maintaining lower central macular thickness post-procedure. Also, there was no statistically significant difference observed in IOP among both the groups after the procedure.

So, the research concluded equal efficacy of Loteprednol Etabonate and Bromfenac on central macular thickness and other parameters post Nd YAG capsulotomy procedure.

References

1. Shetty NK, Sridhar S. Study of variation in intraocular pressure spike (IOP) following Nd- YAG laser capsulotomy. *J Clin Diagn Res* 2016;10:NC09-12.
2. Kraff MC, Sanders DR, McGuigan L, et al. Inhibition of blood-aqueous barrier breakdown with diclofenac. A fluorophotometric study. *Arch Ophthalmol*1990; 108:380–3.
3. Frezotti R, Caporossi A. Pathogenesis of posterior capsule opacification. Part I. Epidemiological and clinical statistical data. *J Cataract Refract Surg.* 1990; 16:347–52
4. Awasthi N, Guo S, Wagner BJ. Posterior capsular opacification: A problem reduced but not yet eradicated. *Arch Ophthalmol*2009; 127:555-62.
5. Gardner KM, Straatsma BR, Pettit TH. Neodymium: YAG laser posterior capsulotomy: The first 100 cases at UCLA. *Ophthalmic Surg*1985; 16:24-8
6. MacEwen CJ, Dutton GN. Neodymium-YAG laser in the management of posterior capsular opacification – Complications and current trends. *Trans Ophthalmol Soc U K* 1986;105(Pt 3):337-44.
7. Hu CY, Woung LC, Wang MC, Jian JH. Influence of laser posterior capsulotomy on anterior chamber depth, refraction, and intraocular pressure. *J Cataract Refract Surg*2000; 26:1183-9
8. Aslam TM, Devlin H, Dhillon B. Use of Nd: YAG laser capsulotomy. *SurvOphthalmol*2003; 48:594-612.
9. Hayashi K, Hayashi H, Nakado F, Hayashi F. Correlation between posterior capsule opacification and visual function before and after Nd:YAG laser posterior capsulotomy. *Am J Ophthalmol.* 2003; 136:720–6.
10. Frezotti R, Caporossi A. Pathogenesis of posterior capsule opacification. Part 1. Epidemiological and clinical statistical data. *J Cataract Refract Surg* 1990; 16:347-52.
11. Meacock WR, Spalton DJ, Stanford MR. Role of cytokines in the pathogenesis of posterior capsule opacification. *Br J Ophthalmol* 2000;84:332-6.
12. Billotte C, Berdeaux G. Adverse clinical consequences of neodymium: YAG laser treatment of posterior capsule opacification. *J Cataract Refract Surg* 2004; 30:2064-71.
13. Murrill CA, Stanfield D, Van Brocklin MD. Capsulotomy. *Optom Clin* 1995;4:69-83
14. Al-Awadi A, Tokko HA, Chan CC, Somani S. Comparison of 2 regimens of loteprednol etabonate and bromfenac for cataract surgery. *Canadian Journal of Ophthalmology.* 2019 Jun 1;54(3):388-94.
15. Lee JS, Kim YH, Park YM. The toxicity of nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory eye drops against human corneal epithelial cells in vitro. *J Korean Med Sci.* 2015; 30:1856–64.
16. Elmazlom EM, Khalil HE, Gouda AT. Central Macular Thickness Changes Following Laser Posterior Capsulotomy Measured by Optical Coherence Tomography. *Egyptian Journal of Medical Research.* 2022 Jan 1;3(1):200-9.
17. Parajuli A, Joshi P, Subedi P, Pradhan C. Effect of Nd: YAG laser posterior capsulotomy on intraocular pressure, refraction, anterior chamber depth, and macular thickness. *Clinical ophthalmology.* 2019 Jun 6:945-52.
18. Cheolwon, Moon., Dong-Geun, Park., Min, Sagong. Effect of Topical Bromfenac as a Treatment of Cystoid Macular Edema Following Pars Plana Vitrectomy. *Journal of The Korean Ophthalmological Society,* (2020).;61(12):1467-1476. doi: 10.3341/JKOS.2020.61.12.1467.
19. Amon M, Busin M. Loteprednol etabonate ophthalmic suspension 0.5%: Efficacy and safety for postoperative anti-inflammatory use. *Int Ophthalmol*2012; 32:507–517.